

Synthesis and anticonvulsant activity of halo-substituted aryl urea and thioureas

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Abstract : Halo-substituted arylureas have been prepared by condensation of halo-substituted primary arylamine with sodium cyanate and halo-substituted arylthioureas have been prepared by condensation of halo-substituted primary arylamine with ammonium thiocyanate in presence of acid. The structures of compounds synthesized have been confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral data. Their anticonvulsant activity was evaluated, *p*-bromophenyl urea and *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-bromophenyl thioureas were found to be most active in the maximal electro shock (MES) test. *p*-Bromophenyl derivatives were found least neurotoxic in the rotorod test. The results were compared with standard drug phenytoin.

Keywords : Aryl urea, thiourea, synthesis, phenytoin.

Introduction

Ureas and thioureas are the compounds containing a wide spectrum of biological activities¹⁻⁵, possessing antimicrobial^{1,2}, antitubercular⁴, anticancer⁵ etc. activities. Thompson *et al.*⁶ synthesized *N*-substituted isoquinolinyl-*N'*-substituted phenylureas and thioureas, were found useful for the treatment and/or prophylaxis of anxiety, mania, depression, panic disorders and/or aggression, disorders associated with a subarachnoid hemorrhage or neural shock, the affects associated with withdrawal from the substances of abuse such as cocaine, nicotine, alcohols and benzodiazepines, disorders treatable and/or preventable with anticonvulsive agents such as post traumatic epilepsy, Parkinson's disease, psychosis, migraine, cerebral ischemia, Alzheimer's disease etc. The sulphur analogous of ureas have been synthesized for its increased lipophilic character. Thioureas are extremely potent compounds, the biological activity of thioureas has been reviewed by Pandeya *et al.*^{7,8}, which exhibited antibacterial, antithyroidal and hypoglycemic activities.

The reaction sequence of ureas⁹ is outlined in Scheme 1 and the reaction sequence of thioureas^{10,11} is outlined

in Scheme 2. In both the reactions, starting compound is halo-substituted aniline which is reacted with NaCNO and NH₄CNS in presence of acid to give ureas and thioureas respectively.

R = *o*-Cl, *m*-Cl, *p*-Cl, *o*-Br, *m*-Br, *p*-Br

Scheme 1

R = *o*-Cl, *m*-Cl, *p*-Cl, *p*-Br

Scheme 2

Table 1. Anticonvulsant activity data of compounds

Sl. no.	Compd.	R.	Molecular formula	MES test (Animals protected)			Rotorod test (Neurotoxic dose) (mg/kg)	ED ₅₀ in MES (mg/kg)	
				Dose (mg/kg)	0.5 h	4 h			24 h
1.	1a	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₂ Cl	100	0/3	0/3	0/3	250	80
2.	1b	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₂ Cl	100	0/3	0/3	0/3	200	70
3.	1c	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₂ Cl	100	0/3	0/3	0/3	300	80
4.	1d	<i>o</i> -Br	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₂ Br	100	0/3	0/3	0/3	300	100
5.	1e	<i>m</i> -Br	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₂ Br	100	0/3	0/3	0/3	200	70
6.	1f	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₂ Br	100	3/3	2/3	2/3	1000	30
7.	2a	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₇ H ₇ N ₂ SCl	100	1/3	0/3	0/3	400	-
8.	2b	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₇ H ₇ N ₂ SCl	100	0/3	0/3	0/3	50	-
9.	2c	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₇ H ₇ N ₂ SCl	100	3/3	2/3	1/3	100	100
10.	2d	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₇ H ₇ N ₂ SBr	100	3/3	2/3	2/3	500	50
11.	Standard drug phenytoin			100	3/3	2/3	0/3	490	6.32

Screening for anticonvulsant activity :

Electroshock method¹² :

The albino rats of either sex, weighing 100–125 g were used. Food was withdrawn 12–15 h before commencing the experiment, while water was withdrawn immediately before the experiment. Maximal seizures were induced through delivering current AC in a pulse of 6 Hz via corneal electrodes at 50 mA for 0.2 s. The animals which showed positive hind limb extensor response were used for testing. Maximal seizures were induced after 0.5 h, 4 h and 24 h of drug administration. Each testing compound is administered (i.p.) as solution in polyethylene glycol in logarithmic dose of 100 mg/kg to animals in groups of three and protections calculated. Thus each MES value is the average of three separate group protections. Pretreatment with effective anticonvulsant drug results the abolition of hind limb tonic extensor spasm. The data were compared by standard drug phenytoin and given in Table 1. The test has predictive value for drug of potential therapeutic value in the management of grandmal epilepsy.

Rotorod test :

Neurotoxicity of the compound was determined by rotorod test. Albino mice weighing 25–30 g were used and trained to stay on an accelerating rotorod, that rotorod at 10 revolutions per minute. The rod diameter was 3.2 cm. Trained animals were given intraperitoneally test compounds. After 30 min mice were placed on rotorod to

measure the effect of the drug on motor performance. The dose at which animals fell off, the rotorod was determined. *p*-Bromophenyl urea and *p*-bromophenyl thiourea showed least toxicity with extended duration of action in MES test.

ED₅₀^{14,15} (effective dose for 50% animals) of the compounds also have been determined. Five logarithmically spaced doses of compound were administered (i.p.) to animals in a group of ten, to cover 0–100% protection, and the dose required to protect 50% of the animals (ED₅₀) was determined graphically. The data are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries, compared with the literature values, which are in generally in agreement with the observed values. IR spectral study was done on PCFT spectrophotometer using KBr disc, PMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Burker AC-300 MHz FT spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer. Micro analysis of all these compounds were with in ±0.4%.

2-Chlorophenyl urea (1a) :

2-Chloroaniline (0.1 mol) was dissolved in 10 ml of glacial acetic acid and diluted to 100 ml in distilled water. To this a solution of 0.1 mol sodium cyanate in 50 ml of warm distilled water was added and allowed to stand for 30 min, cooled in ice bath and again allowed to stand

for same time. The crystallised product was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol to give **1a**, m.p. 150 °C; yield 85% (Found : C, 49.63; H, 4.41; N, 16.78. $C_7H_7ON_2Cl$ requires : C, 49.26; H, 4.13; N, 16.42%); IR (KBr) : 3420 (NH_2), 3020 (C-H), 1650 (C=O); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : 6.4 (1H, bs, NH), 8.15 (2H, bs, $CONH_2$), 7.4 (4H, m, aromatic); Mass : m/z 170.50 (M^+).

Other compounds **1b-f** were synthesized similarly.

4-Bromophenyl urea (**1f**) :

m.p. 227 °C; yield 89% (Found : C, 39.00; H, 3.01; N, 12.65. $C_7H_7ON_2Br$ requires : C, 39.07; H, 3.28; N, 13.03%); IR (KBr) : 3420 (NH_2), 3000 (C-H), 1660 (C=O), 1550 (NH bend), 860 (C-Br); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : 6.4 (1H, bs, NH), 8.1 (2H, bs, $CONH_2$), 7.56 (4H, m, aromatic); Mass : m/z 215 (M^+).

4-Chlorophenyl thiourea (**2c**) :

0.1 mol of 4-chloroaniline was dissolved in 10 ml of conc. HCl and diluted to 100 ml in distilled water. To this a solution of 0.1 mol NH_4CNS in 50 ml of warm distilled water was added and allowed to stand for 30 min, cooled in ice bath and again allowed to stand for next 30 min. Thus obtained crystallised product was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from boiling water to give **2c**, m.p. 159 °C; yield 84% (Found : C, 45.19; H, 3.62; N, 14.95. $C_7H_7N_2SCL$ requires : C, 45.02; H, 3.78; N, 15.01%); IR (KBr) : 3410 (NH_2 asym), 3300 (NH_2 sym), 3020 (C-H), 1190 (C=S), 870 (C-Br); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : 6.5 (1H, bs, NH), 6.8 (2H, bs, $CSNH_2$), 7.5 (4H, m, aromatic); Mass : m/z 186.50 (M^+).

Other compounds **2a-d** were synthesized similarly.

4-Bromophenyl thiourea (**2d**) :

m.p. 171 °C; yield 76.5% (Found : C, 36.10; H, 3.28; N, 12.01. $C_7H_7N_2SBr$ requires : C, 36.35; H, 3.05; N, 12.12%); IR (KBr) : 3420 (NH_2), 3020 (C-H), 1280 (N-CS-N), 1200 (C=S), 860 (C-Br); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : 6.5 (1H, bs, NH), 6.8 (2H, bs, $CSNH_2$), 7.5 (4H, m, aromatic); Mass : m/z 231 (M^+).

Results and discussion

In the MES test *o*-chlorophenyl thiourea (**2a**) showed 33% anticonvulsant activity only after 0.5 h of drug administration at a dose of 100 mg/kg. *p*-Chlorophenyl thio-

urea (**2c**) and *p*-bromophenyl thiourea (**2d**) showed 100% anticonvulsant activity after 0.5 h and 66% activity after 4 h of drug administration for the same dose which shows equal potency as standard drug. Again **2c** and **2d** showed 33% and 66% protections respectively after 24 h of drug administration at which phenytoin was found inactive. In the urea group only *p*-bromophenyl urea (**1f**) was found active and same potent as second. Compounds **1f**, **2c** and **2d** were found active with extended duration of 24 h where standard drug is not found active.

p-Bromophenyl urea (**1f**) and *p*-bromophenyl thiourea (**2d**) are found least neurotoxic among all synthesized compounds. These compounds (**1f** and **2d**) are not found neurotoxic below the doses of 1000 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg respectively and less neurotoxic than phenytoin. Finally **1f** and **2d** showed ED_{50} values of 30 mg/kg and 50 mg/kg respectively, therefore very less effective than the ED_{50} of standard drug. *p*-Bromo derivatives were found least neurotoxic in the rotorod test and considered best in the MES test with extended duration of anticonvulsant activity.

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